

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4277864

The economic justification of the public administration decisions in the area of the national security and defence

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Annotation. The study develops the toolkit to make economically justified the public administration decisions in the area of the national security and defense, which fundamentally aims to maximize the impact of activities on the public administration of the security and defense sector due to minimizing or optimizing the expenditures of their operation and their relevant tasks. by appointment. The authors suggest applying the approaches, principles and methods of military-economic analysis to the decision-making process of the public administration in the mentioned area. Such toolkit is structured according to the relevant stages of the decision-making process and the estimation of its effectiveness by the certain criterion and indicators at each of the identified stages.

The current period in Ukraine is characterized by the fact that the issues of public administration decisions in the area of the national security and defense are becoming more and more relevant, since our state is at the epicenter of threats of various nature: military, security, economic, criminogenic, technogenic, epidemiological, etc. The state regulation in the area of the national security and defense can be considered as an influence of the public authorities with the help of various means (forms, methods and tools) on providing the safe life of a human and a citizen, the steady development of the social relations in society, the protection of the constitutional system of the state, prevention and/or minimization of the consequences of crisis and extraordinary situations of the socio-political, socio-economic, technogenic and natural character; the system of the legal, organizational, regulatory and control measures of the state in order to respond to the relevant internal and external threats [1, Art. 51].

The system of the national social security is an open, dynamic, social system, the purpose of which is to create the conditions to implement the national interests, provide the integrity of the public body and the ability of the state to defend the mentioned interests [2, p. 117]. Basing on such a point of view, in the system of national security, as well as in any social system, the public administration is a combination of organizational influences, which provide the functioning of the objects and subjects of the mentioned system. That is, firstly, the public administration in the area of providing the national security and defense is a subsystem within a certain social system, which is considered to have the specific functions due to the re-establishing of the system. Secondly, one of the main functions is to provide the functioning of the relationships between the elements of a system itself, its objects and subjects. Thirdly, the public administration should provide the regulation of the elements of the system itself, which determines its active nature.

The state policy in the field of the national security and defense is directed at providing the military, foreign, state, economic, information, environmental security, cybersecurity of Ukraine, etc. [3]. The mentioned state policy is implemented through the respective public

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administration decisions, including those about the use of resources for the functioning of the security and defense sector.

The problems of the public administration, legal and regulatory support, targeted and strategic planning and programming in the area of the national security and defense were considered in the scientific works of Belay S., Bondarenko O., Gorbulin V., Datsyuk A., Degtyar A., Dombrovnska S., Litvinenko O., Kachinsky A., Poltorank S., Sytnik G., Cherkashin O. and others. Therefore, in the following scientific works [2, 4, 5] the conceptual foundations of the public administration of the national security were explored. The second group of the scientific works [6 - 9] are devoted to the state strategy and the programme-targeted planning of the national security of Ukraine. The authors of the next ones [10 - 12] have analyzed the problems and justified the directions of improving the mechanisms of the public administration to resist the crisis phenomena of the socio-economic nature. The following articles and monographs [13, 14] were devoted to the mechanisms of the public administration in the are of the national security.

Despite the integrity and depth of the scientific works on the issues of the public administration in the area of the national security and defense, the issues of an economic justification of the public administration decisions in this area remain poorly examined. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to develop a toolkit for an economic justification for the public administration decisions in the area of the national security and defense.

The rational use of resources for the functioning of the security and defense sector formations is primarily provided by the economic justification of the decisions in this area. These are based on comparing the beneficial effect of their implementation and the respective costs, i.e. on the basis of the indicators of a military-economic efficiency and methods of a military-economic analysis. The military-economic analysis assumes the estimation of the two groups of indicators, one of which is reflecting the effect aspect of the public administration decisions and the other one of which is reflecting the economic aspects (of cost and of time) of the mentioned measure. The effect aspect is determined by the purpose of the activity, which comes from the objective needs of the practice. The purpose is understood as the desired condition or the achieved result by any structural element. Preferably, during the conducting of the analysis the level of achievement of the goal should be quantitatively measured, which increases the analyticity of the obtained results [15]. The economic aspect consists of the indicators of the amount of required or spent resources and the indicators of the duration of achieving the goal. The necessity of using the time indicator arise due to inability of an immediate satisfaction with all the resources needed to achieve the goal, and an immediate fulfilling of all the work which is a part of the event. It should be taken into account that there may be many ways to achieve the goal, so the terms of achieving the goal and the amount of resources will be different. Therefore, the military-economic analysis generally assumes an estimation of three following indicators: *effect-cost-time* [15]. When solving the private tasks of the economic justification of public administration decisions in the area of the national security and defense, it is advisable to estimate only the *effect-cost* indicators.

There are two groups of methods used for military-economic justification of decisions:

1. Optimization methods;
2. Methods of comparative estimation of options.

For difficult tasks, it is possible to use the methods of both groups.

The optimization methods are used in those cases where the task is to determine the optimal parameters of the solution variant from all of their possible set, that is, the variants themselves in the original data are missing. Usually there are two types of such tasks:

1. Achieving the maximum beneficial effect at a given expenditure of resources. This is called the resource allocation task. Its mathematical model looks like:

$$W(X) \rightarrow \max;$$

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$$C(X) \leq C_o;$$

$$G(X) \leq G_o,$$

where $W(X)$, $C(X)$, $G(X)$ is a function of beneficial effect, cost function and function of solution parameter restriction respectively;

X is a vector of solution parameters;

C_o is a given value of the selected resources;

G_o means restrictions on the other factors (time, specific conditions, etc.);

2. Achieving the needed beneficial effect (W_o) with the minimal expenditures, which is called the resource minimization task:

$$C(X) \rightarrow \min;$$

$$W(X) \geq W_o;$$

$$G(X) \leq G_o.$$

The functions $W(X)$ in the first task, and $C(X)$ in the second one are called targeted functions and the others are called restriction functions. The targeted function reflects the goal of optimization, and the restriction function reflects the range of valid values of X -parameters, that is, the valid solutions, the number of which can be infinite. Knowledge of specific types of all functions is required for formation of these tasks, which is quite a difficult task. Mathematical statistics, modeling, expert methods, etc. are used in finding the functions. The optimization tasks are solved by the classical methods of differentiation, methods of mathematical programming (linear, non-linear, dynamic, stochastic, etc.), methods of optimal planning, etc. The choice of method is determined by the contents of the task and the type of its functions.

The advantage of the optimization methods is to obtain the best, or optimal parameters of the solutions from all the possible ones which bring the extremum of the targeted function. The disadvantage is the complexity of obtaining the analytical relationships, that is, the resistance functions and the targeted function, and also the further solution of the tasks.

The methods of comparative estimation of options involve the presence of variants of the solution with the known parameters. The task is to choose the economically appropriate option. The choice is made by comparing the beneficial effect and the expenditures of each option.

The tasks of this type can be divided into two groups:

1. The fundamentally new problems, the need of solving which has a separate justification. Effect and/or cost limit values are usually given. Two or more solution variants are offered, from which an economically appropriate and effective option is selected.

2. The tasks of updating and improvement of an existing object of analysis, which has its own parameters of effect and expenditures. Here the task of the economic estimation of the feasibility of the variant of taking an action is solved. In this case, there may be only one option, because the second one is always given, namely not taking any actions. If there are two or more options, the task is to choose the most economically appropriate from the whole set, but regarding the variant of not taking the actions.

The division of tasks into two mentioned groups is conditional and the tasks can move from one group to another. In our opinion, the solution of the problems of economic justification of public administration decisions in the area of national security and defense should be done by the method of the comparative estimation, which generally includes the following stages:

1. Formulation of the problem, formation and analysis of its solution variants;
2. Determination of the indicators of useful effect and expenditures for each variant;

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3. Estimation of the necessity and bringing up the options into such form, which can be used for comparison;

4. Justification of the criterion for choosing the variant of the decision and calculation of the criterion indicators;

5. Choosing of a solution and analyzing the results.

On the first stage, a task, which requires a public administration decision, is formulated in an informative form, and the possible parameters of its solution are specified, that is, the requirements for the indicators of effect and expenditures. There must be at least two options.

On the second stage, each of the options determines the performance and cost metrics. Here it is possible to pre-select options for the further consideration if the limit values of the calculated indicators are given.

Generally, the indicators of effect and expenditures are different for the options. According to the method of comparative estimation, it is necessary to compare the variants for the useful effect, that is providing the equality of effect for all the variants. The equation may not be conducted if all the variants satisfy the requirements of the conditions of the task by the effect, or ensure its performance.

The analysis of necessity and comparison of options is conducted on the third stage. If the need for comparison is identified, the comparison includes:

1. Choosing the option that has the maximum effect value (W_{max});

2. Determining the ways to increase the effect of the other options to the value of W_{max} by changing the parameters which determine it, including by:

- Resource building of options (number of the used equipment and machinery, personnel, material resources, etc.);

- Changes in the operating modes of machinery and equipment, tactical techniques of the task performance, etc.

3. Listing the indicators of expenditures by the comparison options.

Choosing a comparison method is quite a challenging task and is determined by specific conditions. As a result of comparison of the effect values of all variants will be the same and the expenditures will be different. It may occur that the goal of comparing the options has not been achieved, but the solution of the problem in this case does not stop.

On the fourth stage, the criterion for selecting options is formed. If a comparison has already been conducted or there is no need for this, the choice is made by the indicators of expenditures. The following criterion is used on this stage:

1. The minimum expenditures to implement options. The criterion allows to choose the economically feasible option, but does not give an estimate of the economic effect.

2. The positive value of the economic effect of using the one option over another, or $W_i > 0$. The criterion is an addition to the first one and allows to estimate the economic effect of the implementation of one option compared to another. Here the option with the highest expenditures is chosen, which is taken as the basic one (B_0). Then the economic effect of any i -th option is equal to:

$$W_i = B - B_i, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (1)$$

The economic effect can be calculated for the entire period of operation, that is, the total economic effect - W_0 , and for one year - W_p , taking into account and without taking into account the time factor.

1. For the variants which are not compared by the beneficial effect, but its consideration is necessary, the choice of the option is made by the criterion of the minimum specific costs, that is the cost per unit of the beneficial effect - B_{ni} , namely $\min B_{ni}$, with:

$$B_{ni} = \frac{B_i}{W_i}, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (2)$$

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This task is usually solved during the economic estimation of the objects which have the same functional purpose: the tools of measuring, communication, control, military and special equipment, weapons and special means, etc. The conditions of specific application of changes generally are not considered.

On the final fifth stage, the economically appropriate variant of the decision according to the chosen criterion is selected and analyzed. As a result of this stage, as well as other ones, it is possible to return to the previous stages, starting from the first one.

The advantage of methods of comparative estimation of options is that the decision to choose the best option from the considered options (including not taking the actions) will always be made. The methodology is easier here compared to the optimization methods. The disadvantage of these methods is that the obtained solution may not be overall optimal because not all the possible solutions are considered.

In the everyday work of the security and defense sector, there is a need for economic justification of actions aiming to improve them. Usually, one option is proposed and the task is to estimate the economic feasibility of conducting it. Such a task is a special case of a comparative economic estimation task because the proposed option is compared to the option of not taking the actions. For the proposed action within the object of analysis, the following indicators are calculated:

- gain (change) of the beneficial effect – ΔW ;
- simultaneous expenditures to take the actions – ΔB ;
- change of the running expenditures – ΔC .

Generally, the values of ΔW and ΔB are positive and ΔC is negative. But there may be the other combinations, for example, all quantities are positive. The calculation of the value of the change of the running expenditures is carried out in those cases when their change occurs, which significantly simplifies the calculation.

Let us consider two tasks of estimation the feasibility of such actions. The beneficial effect of the first task does not change or is indifferent to the specific conditions, that is $\Delta W = 0$. Here it is possible to use the criterion of a positive economic effect. This means that an action is considered economically effective if its one-time expenditures are overlaped with the savings of expenditures of operating the facility after taking the actions, counting on the entire operating period (W_3) or on one year (W_p), $W_{3(p)} > 0$.

If the time factor is not considered, the effect is calculated with the following formula:

$$W_3 = DB - DC \cdot T; W_p = \frac{DB}{T} - DC, \quad (3)$$

where ΔC means the annual savings on running expenditures;

T is a period of taking the action, years.

If the factor of time is taken into account, then the values of ΔC and ΔB , as well as, respectively, $W_{3(p)}$ are calculated on the basis of the coefficients of bringing different expenditures to a single point in time by conventional methods.

In the second task, the gain of the beneficial effect takes place and should be compulsory considered, that is $\Delta W > 0$. Then the earlier mentioned general method of comparative estimation is applied. In particular, a comparison of effect variants is carried out, that is, a known, preferred variant of actions is considered to provide the same gain of the beneficial effect ΔW . For example, the additional facilities, reservations, etc. Then the proposed variant and the variant for comparison are analyzed by the considered method.

If the equation is complicated, it is advisable to use the criterion of reducing the unit value of the beneficial effect after taking an action, which looks like:

$$\frac{B_1}{W_1} > \frac{(B_1 + DB)}{W_1 + DW} \text{ а } \frac{DW}{W_1} > \frac{DB}{B_1}, \quad (4)$$

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where B_I i W_I are the indicators of the total expenditures and effect for the analyzed object before taking an action calculated over the same time period;

ΔB means total expenditures on taking an action.

This criterion means that an action is considered to be economically appropriate, if the relative gain of the beneficial effect is more than the increase of the total expenditures. To improve the reliability of the criterion the minimum value of such excess is given, which is based on the specific conditions of the task.

Therefore, the developed toolkit allows us to make economically justified public administration decisions in the field of the national security and defense, which fundamentally aims to achieve the maximum effect from the work of public administration of the formation of the security and defense sector while minimizing or optimizing the expenditures for their functioning and fulfilling of their respective tasks of their purpose. In addition, the authors propose to apply the approaches, principles and methods of military-economic analysis to make the public administration decisions in the mentioned area. This toolkit is structured according to the relevant stages of the decision-making process and the estimation of its effectiveness by the defined criterion and indicators at each of the identified stages.

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